

Empirically measuring algorithmically embodied emissions of information access systems

Florian Meier^a and David Elsweiler^b

^a Aalborg University, Copenhagen, Denmark

^b University of Regensburg, Regensburg, Germany

1. Introduction

The rise of generative AI has raised concerns about the environmental impact of AI and machine learning due to high energy consumption and associated greenhouse gas emissions (Bender et al., 2021; Luccioni et al., 2024). Luccioni et al. (2023) adopt a "cradle-to-grave" approach in their life cycle assessment, categorizing emissions into *operational emissions*, arising from algorithm training and inference and *embodied emissions*, linked to data center construction and hardware manufacturing.

Haider et al. (2022) add a third category: *algorithmically embodied emissions* (AEE). AEE refers to emissions resulting from algorithmic curation, where carbon-intensive recommendations influence users' choices and perceptions of climate change. Using Google as an example, Haider et al. (2022) argue that default query interpretation, result selection, and ranking often prioritize unsustainable content, thereby normalizing a high-carbon narrative (Berglez and Olausson 2023). This bias toward consumerism and carbon-intensive values is especially pronounced when different relevance criteria (subject, topical, and societal) collide (Sundin et al., 2022). While sustainable information is available, finding it is a complex task that requires longer search sessions and a greater awareness of climate issues from users.

AEE can be seen as a second-order algorithmic harm, adding to the list of biases and stereotypes related to religion, gender, or race that many systems exhibit (Noble, 2018; Metaxa et al., 2021a). However, the contexts, circumstances, and extent to which AEE arise have not been systematically studied, and a framework for conceptualizing and investigating this phenomenon is still lacking.

In this short talk, we aim to introduce a draft framework for empirically measuring the AEE of algorithm-driven information access systems. We will do so by linking to relevant research in the fields of IR and RecSys, especially with respect to research on fairness and diversity (Ekstrand et al., 2022), as sustainable information in SERPs is not equally well represented due to biased ranking algorithms. From a methodological perspective, we identify two main approaches for studying the issue: (1) audits and simulations, and (2) user studies. Audits, defined as "[...] repeatedly and systematically querying a system with inputs and observing the corresponding outputs to draw inferences about its opaque inner workings" (Metaxa et al., 2021b, p.288), provide a way to examine both (1a) search engine algorithms and (1b) other AI components driving parts of a system, such as large language models (LLMs). In the context of (1a), we aim to develop scales for evaluating the sustainability of search results, inspired by methods from the literature on other search-related issues, such as the evaluation of news articles, where standardized databases of media outlet reputation have been used to quantify search result quality (Elsweiler et al., 2025). To study (1b), Nadeem et al. (2021)'s work can serve as inspiration for developing a benchmark dataset and corresponding inter- and intra-sentence association tasks to assess the bias of LLMs towards consumerist, unsustainable stereotypes. Finally, in (2), task-based user studies can give insights into how climate-conscious users navigate unsustainable SERPs and what role personalisation plays in this context.

SEASON 2025, September 24–25, 2025, Hamburg, Germany

EMAIL: fmeier@ikp.aau.dk (A. 1); david.elsweiler@ur.de (A. 2)

ORCID: 0000-0001-9408-0686 (A. 1); 0000-0002-5791-0641 (A. 2)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17155939>

© 2025 Copyright for this paper by its authors.

Use permitted under Creative Commons License Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

Our framework offers the potential to study how user search behaviour impacts the downstream emissions generated by search systems, which is, to date, unclear.

2. References

Bender, E. M., Gebru, T., McMillan-Major, A. and Shmitchell, S. (2021). *On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big?* . In Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 610–623. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445922>

Berglez, P., & Olausson, U. (2021). *Climate irresponsibility on social media. A critical approach to “high-carbon visibility discourse.”* Social Semiotics, 33(5), 1011–1025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10350330.2021.1976053>

Ekstrand, M. D., Das, A., Burke, R., and Diaz, F. (2022). *Fairness in information access systems.* Found. Trends Inf. Retr., 16(1–2):1–177. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/15000000079>

Elsweiler, D., Ateia, S., Bink, M., Donabauer, G., Pichel, M. F., Frummet, A., Kruschwitz, U., Losada, D. E., Ludwig, B., Meyer, S. and Presa, N. P. (2025). Query Smarter, Trust Better? Exploring Search Behaviours for Verifying News Accuracy. In Proceedings of the 48th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 515–526. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3726302.3730067>

Haider, J., Rödl, M., & Joosse, S. (2022). *Algorithmically embodied emissions: The environmental harm of everyday life information in digital culture.* 11th International Conference on Conceptions of Library and Information Science, Oslo, Norway, May 29 - June 1, 2022. <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:hb:diva-28904>

Luccioni, A. S., Viguier, S., and Ligozat, A.-L. (2023). *Estimating the carbon footprint of bloom, a 176b parameter language model.* Journal of Machine Learning Research, 24(253):1–15.

Luccioni, S., Jernite, Y., and Strubell, E. (2024). *Power Hungry Processing: Watts Driving the Cost of AI Deployment?* In Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '24). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3658542>

Metaxa, D., Gan, M. A., Goh, S., Hancock, J. and Landay, J. A. (2021). *An Image of Society: Gender and Racial Representation and Impact in Image Search Results for Occupations.* Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact. 5, CSCW1, Article 26 (April 2021), 23 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3449100>

Metaxa, D., Park, J. S., Robertson, R. E., Karahalios, K., Wilson, C., Hancock, J., and Sandvig, C. (2021b). *Auditing algorithms.* Foundations and Trends in Human-Computer Interaction, 14(4):272–344. <https://doi.org/10.1561/1100000008>

Nadeem, M., Bethke, A., and Reddy, S. (2021). *StereoSet: Measuring stereotypical bias in pretrained language models.* In Zong, C., Xia, F., Li, W., and Navigli, R., editors, Proc. of 59th/11th ACL-IJCNLP (Volume 1: Long Papers), pages 5356–5371, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Noble, S. U. (2018). *Algorithms of oppression. How search engines reinforce racism*. New York University Press, New York.

Sundin, O., Lewandowski, D., & Haider, J. (2022). *Whose relevance? Web search engines are multisided relevance machines*. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 73(5), 637–642. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24570>